

ROLE OF EMF DETECTOR FOR THE INVESTIGATION OF LAMBI DEHAR MINES 10KM FAR FROM LIBRARY CHOWK MUSSOORIE

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ABSTRACT There are many unsolved questions which are haunting, these happen from many years. Actually many persons ask do ghosts really exist. In India there are many haunting place as in Kolkata Wipro Company where situated it's really haunted. In India 87% persons believe that ghost is exist all time. As that I visited the place Lambi Dehar Mines and it is infamous one of most haunted places in uttarakhand. This place is a ghost area and by EMF meter and I give rent two two ojhas and they went with me this time. By our research i faced many horror incidents. As I mentioned below.

KEYWORDS :

Introduction-

Lambi Dehar Mines is situated in Khanij Nagar, Mussoorie Range, Uttarakhand 248179. This mines has many paranormal affects. There is a big incident happened date back to 1990, when it said that 50000 mine workers died here in excruciating pain due to inappropriate and mining practices wrongfully and the workers who lived near the mine, died coughing with blood happened lung disorder. Due to this reason the lambi dehar mine in Mussoorie is haunted. The locals have reported that at night the 50,000 dead workers cry they always listen. Some people told that there will be happened many accidents also a helicopter crashed near the mines. So, we investigated about it.

Methods- As our research partner Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai is the expert of Planchet of Ouija Board. So, In amavasya night at 11:30 P.M. we went the Khandar which means ruins of a house after ready for procedure. In this Khandar we stayed in first big room and in 12:30 P.M. Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai is started his Planchet after 45minutes there is a response and we feel there is a negative vibes. So, after Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai directly took his emf meter showed the reading.

Results- The EMF Meter reading was- Field is 83, and max is 129 μ T and min was 82. By this methods we feel the negative vibes and max 129 μ T indicated that there are soo many spirits in this haunted area and this time we listened soo, much crying sound. After we escape from the place.

Discussion- By this research we learned a lesion that never try this dangerous research in this place in amavasya. But in morning there will be no spirit.

Acknowledgement- This research writing skills done by Mansoor Habibullah and practical work done by Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai. As Shyam Prakash Rai is a B.Pharm from Assam DOWNTOWN UNIVERSITY. In this research local peoples helped us soo much.

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Figure 2: Variance ratios for 10km squares containing samples from MEA10 and SEA04.

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